

Academic Indiscipline: An Impediment to Effective Curriculum Implementation on Students in Tertiary Institutions in Delta State, Nigeria

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Abstract

This study investigated academic indiscipline and its impact on effective curriculum implementation in tertiary institutions in Delta State, Nigeria. A descriptive survey research design was employed. The study targeted lecturers and students from both public and private institutions in the state, with a total of 370 participants: 140 lecturers and 230 students. Three research questions and two hypotheses were developed and tested. Data was gathered using a structured questionnaire, the “Students Indiscipline Questionnaire” (SIQ), created by the researcher. The instrument was validated by four experts in Education, Measurement, and Evaluation. Reliability was determined using Cronbach’s alpha, resulting in a coefficient of 0.75, which confirmed the instrument’s reliability. The questionnaires were distributed, and the collected data were analyzed. Descriptive statistics (mean and standard deviation) were used to answer the research questions, while inferential statistics (t-test) were employed to test the hypotheses. The results indicated that both lecturers and students acknowledged the presence of common academic indiscipline behaviors, their causes, and their effects, all of which hinder curriculum implementation. The two hypotheses were confirmed based on the data. The study concluded that academic indiscipline is widespread in tertiary institutions and called for collective efforts to tackle this issue. Recommendations included educating and empowering parents to support their children's education and enhancing counseling services in tertiary institutions.

Keywords: Indiscipline, Tertiary Institution, Curriculum Implementation Impediments.

Introduction

Education is a fundamental human right. Article 26 of the Universal Declaration of Human Rights, which was adopted by the United Nations General Assembly in December 1948, states that every individual has the right to education. It also emphasizes that parents have the primary responsibility for determining the type of education their children should receive. However, such rights cannot be fully realized in an environment marred by disorder and indiscipline within the educational system. Education serves as the cornerstone for meaningful development in any society and remains the primary avenue for both individual and national progress. As stated by Nasara et al. (2021), education is the means through which individuals become productive members of society, acquiring knowledge that helps them realize their potential and contribute to society in a meaningful way. Moreover, education is crucial for achieving the developmental goals of any nation. It is considered a powerful tool for driving socio-cultural, political, and economic advancement, and it is often seen as the key to transformative change, as any significant shift in the intellectual and social fabric of a society must begin with an educational revolution (Cheta & Anekwe, 2010).

The Nigerian education system is structured into several distinct levels: pre-primary, primary, secondary, and tertiary education. Tertiary education refers to formal schooling that takes place after secondary education and includes institutions like universities, colleges of education, polytechnics, and monotechnics. This level of education encompasses all post-secondary programs offered by both public and private institutions, such as universities, technical schools, and vocational centers. Tertiary institutions play an essential role in fostering economic growth, reducing poverty, and promoting collective prosperity. The primary aim of tertiary education is to develop skilled professionals and high-level workforce personnel needed for national development. As outlined in the National Policy on Education (2014), the specific objectives of tertiary education include the following;

1. Contribute to the nation's growth by offering advanced, specialized training for the workforce.
2. Enhance individuals' intellectual capabilities, allowing them to better understand and engage with both their local and global surroundings.
3. Promote and instill core values that are vital for the welfare of individuals and society as a whole.
4. Provide individuals with both practical and intellectual skills, encouraging self-sufficiency and helping them become valuable contributors to society.
5. Encourage academic achievement and active participation in community development.
6. Reinforce and support national unity.
7. Promote understanding and cooperation, both nationally and internationally.

Unfortunately, tertiary education which is one of the basic pillars for achieving development and improving the capabilities of our youths and preparing them for the future is bedeviled with all sorts of problems ranging from indiscipline to socio-political problems, through personal, to system/procedural which has to a large extent affected academic excellence of students in tertiary institutions. It is therefore imperative that the curriculum be structured or packaged to attain the aforementioned goals. The term "curriculum" refers to all the learning experiences organized by the school to guide students toward achieving specific educational goals. The curriculum can therefore be viewed as all the experiences provided by the school for the achievement of goals of education. Different curricula have been developed to achieve educational objectives, and their success depends on proper implementation. For a country to make progress in science and technology, it is crucial to prioritize the effective implementation of the curriculum at all levels.

Curriculum implementation is generally acknowledged to be one of the problematic areas of institutionalized education (Oyovwi, 2022). It is the stage when the curriculum itself, viewed as an educational program is put into practice. The learners is the center of attention in the course of implementing the curriculum because it is the learners that attains the planned intended experiences, knowledge, skills, attitude, abilities and dispositions. The teacher plays a key role as the main facilitator in the curriculum implementation process, responsible for choosing and combining the different knowledge components specified in the curriculum. The teacher ensures that there is interaction between the learner and the syllabus, the instructional materials, teaching environment and ability to adopt instructional strategies that are more students' centered so as to promote critical thinking and student's participation (Oyovwi & Iroteraye-Adjekpovu, 2021).

The roles of both teachers and learners are essential for the effective implementation of the curriculum, as the overall quality of education in any society is closely linked to the capabilities of its teachers and students. This suggests that, regardless of how well a curriculum is designed, its success and effectiveness ultimately depend on the preparedness of the teachers—both in terms of skill and

commitment—to engage learners in all the activities outlined in the curriculum (Oyovwi, 2012). However, most curriculum have failed to bring desirable changes not because they were deficient but for academic indiscipline among teachers and learners.

Education has become a key area of focus for government attention, alongside other priorities. However, for curriculum objectives to be successfully achieved, discipline must be upheld within the school system, as effective teaching and learning cannot occur in an environment characterized by indiscipline (Okebukola, 2017).

Indiscipline is evident in various aspects of human and social interactions and has posed significant challenges both in schools and society as a whole. It is a pervasive issue that has deeply affected the fabric of society. The Oxford Advanced Learner's Dictionary (2000) defines indiscipline as the inability to control the behavior of a group. It essentially refers to an individual or group's failure to follow the set rules and regulations of a specific system. In the educational context, academic indiscipline refers to behaviors that violate the norms, rules, or expectations within academic institutions, such as cheating, disruptions, academic dishonesty, lateness, and absenteeism. Mohammed (2018) observed that student indiscipline is a worldwide issue, reflecting behavior that strays from commonly accepted standards in various social environments, such as homes and schools (Amy, 2017). It involves not adhering to the rules, policies, procedures, or regulations of an institution or society. Indiscipline reflects a lack of order and control, often manifesting as partial or total deviation from expected behavior.

Schools and educational institutions are meant to prepare students and equip them with the necessary tools for development, yet indiscipline has become widespread among students, especially in tertiary institutions (Gitorne et al., 2013). The increasing prevalence of this issue not only affects academic performance but also hinders the successful implementation of the curriculum. Disruptive behaviors, such as riots, vandalism, and disregard for the law, have become common in schools. These actions foster an environment that undermines effective learning and curriculum delivery. It is troubling to witness the extent of damage caused by academic indiscipline, as it hampers teachers' ability to implement the curriculum and distracts students, who engage in various harmful social vices that undermine the school system.

Ogunmade (2015) noted that indiscipline in schools has led to numerous challenges, with insufficient measures in place to address the issue effectively. He further argued that the problem of indiscipline among students is one that needs to be addressed collectively by parents, schools, and society. According to Ogunmade, children are born innocent, and their behavior becomes influenced and shaped as they interact with their homes, peer groups, and environments such as schools. Hence, Lukeman & Hamadi (2014) posited that disciplinary measures should be enforced in schools to check properly student's behaviors which are at variance with the norms and standard of the schools.

Ogunmade (2015) viewed that indiscipline in our school today is sometimes a projection or maturation of what began at home. He asserted that a child from broken marriage is very harsh, unhappy, insecure and frustrated to the extent of wandering about, idling, pick pocketing fighting etc. These acts that are imbibed will be taken to school and they influence others. This causes negative effect on their academic performance. It is therefore imperative that for effective curriculum implementation in the tertiary institutions, a proactive measures be taken to eliminate the menace of indiscipline in tertiary institutions.

Hence this study focused on student's indiscipline, an impediment to effective curriculum content implementation among students in tertiary institutions in Delta State, Nigeria

Purpose of the Study

Indiscipline, an impediment to effective curriculum implementation among students in tertiary institutions was the major purpose of the study. Specifically, it tried to:

- i. determine some common indiscipline exhibited that constitute impediments to effective curriculum implementation among students.
- ii. Find out the causes of indiscipline exhibited that constitute impediments to effective curriculum implementation among students.
- iii. Determine the effects of indiscipline in effective curriculum implementation among students.

Research Questions

1. What are some common undisciplined behavior exhibited which impedes effective curriculum implementation on students?
2. What are the causes of undisciplined behavior exhibited which impedes effective curriculum implementation on students?
3. What are the effects of undisciplined on the effective implementation of the curriculum on students?

Research Hypotheses

1. There is no significant difference in the mean score of teachers and students on causes of undisciplined behavior exhibited by students which impedes effective curriculum implementation on students.
2. There is no significant difference in the mean scores of teachers and students on the effects of undisciplined on effective curriculum implementation on students.

Methodology

This study explored indiscipline as an obstacle to the effective implementation of the curriculum among students in tertiary institutions in Delta State. A descriptive survey research design was employed for the study. The population included all lecturers and students from tertiary institutions throughout Delta State, Nigeria. The sample included 140 lecturers and 230 students. A simple random sampling technique, using withdrawal and replacement, was employed to select the participants. Data were collected through a structured questionnaire titled "Students Indiscipline Questionnaire" (SIQ), created by the researcher. The questionnaire was validated by four experts in the fields of Education, Measurement, and Evaluation, who reviewed its content and face validity. Their feedback was used to improve the final version of the instrument. To assess its reliability, the questionnaire was administered to a group of students and lecturers outside the study area, resulting in a reliability coefficient of 0.75, determined using Cronbach's Alpha. Five research assistants from the selected institutions helped administer the instrument. Responses were collected and analyzed using a 4-point response scale, with scores of 2.50 and above deemed acceptable, while those below 2.50 were discarded. The research questions were analyzed descriptively using mean and standard deviation, and hypotheses were tested inferentially using t-test statistics at a 0.05 significance level.

Results

What are some common undisciplined behaviors exhibited which impedes effective curriculum implementation on students?

Table 1: Undisciplined Behaviors Exhibited by Students

S/N	ITEMS	N	MEAN	SD
1	Disrespecting Lecturers	250	2.97	1.18
2	Truancy	250	2.80	1.29
3	Failure to do Assignment	250	3.33	1.29
4	Examination malpractice	250	3.61	0.64
5	Drug abuse	250	2.21	0.47
6	Fighting	250	2.20	0.89
7	Engaging in pre-marital sex	250	2.76	1.39
8	Snatching or stealing other learners property	250	2.04	1.11
9	Vandalism	250	2.80	1.14
10	Cultism and rape	250	2.76	1.32
11	Disobedient to constituted authority	250	2.50	1.15
12	Lateness to lectures and absenteeism	250	2.39	1.10
13	Cohabiting with opposite sex	250	3.65	1.20
14	Indecent dressing	250	2.52	1.29

From Table 1, out of fourteen items, ten items were identified by respondents as common academic indiscipline behavior exhibited by students which serve as obstacles to the successful implementation of the curriculum. The ten items have a benchmark of 2.50 and above, hence the acceptance.

What are the causes of undisciplined behavior exhibited which impedes effective curriculum implementation on students?

Table 2: Cause of Undisciplined Behaviors Exhibited by Students.

S/N	ITEMS	N	MEAN	SD
1	Broken homes	250	2.80	1.14
2	Single parenting	250	3.66	1.26
3	The failure of parents to meet the financial needs of their children or wards	250	3.86	0.39
4	Inability of parents to properly monitor and supervise children/ward academic work	250	2.76	1.39
5	Excessive attachment to watching film	250	2.76	1.39
6	Family background with low interest to education	250	2.52	1.29
7	Peer influence	250	3.52	1.29
8	Inadequate school facilities	250	2.50	1.15
9	Poor Lecturer-students relationship	250	2.80	1.19
10	Improper class management	250	2.76	1.39
11	Lecturers Absenteeism	250	2.39	1.10
12	Lecturers moral relationship with female students	250	2.70	1.28

As shown in Table 2, eleven out of the twelve items were identified as causes of academic indiscipline behaviors exhibited by students, which obstruct the successful implementation of the curriculum. The eleven items have a benchmark of 2.50 and above, hence the acceptance.

What are the effects of undisciplined on the effective implementation of the curriculum on students?

Table 3: Effects of Undisciplined behavior on effective curriculum implementation

S/N	ITEMS	N	MEAN	SD
1	Inadequate coverage of the curriculum content	250	2.91	0.35
2	Inability to concentrate in class	250	2.80	1.14
3	Lack of comprehension of the curriculum content	250	2.76	1.39
4	Poor academic performance of students	250	3.52	1.29
5	School drop out	250	2.52	1.29
6	Production of half-baked students	250	2.50	1.15
7	Disruption of the academic program	250	2.52	1.29
8	Impersonation	250	2.50	1.15

From the above table (3), all the respondents attested to the effects of the academic indiscipline on the successful implementation of the curriculum, which act as obstacles. The eight items have a benchmark of 2.50 and above, hence the acceptance.

There is no significant difference in the mean score of teachers and students on causes of undisciplined behavior exhibited by students which impedes effective curriculum implementation on students.

Table 4: t-test analysis of the mean score of teachers and students on causes of indiscipline which constitute impediment of effective curriculum implementation

Variables	N	\bar{X}	SD	Dif	t.cal	L-cal	Decision
Lecturers	140	4.64	0.22	369	0.44	1.95	Accept
Students	230	4.65	0.24				

Table 4 shows that the t-calculated value was 0.44, while the t-critical value was 1.95 at a 0.05 level of significance. Since the t-calculated value is smaller than the t-critical value, the hypothesis was accepted. Thus, there is no significant difference between the mean scores of lecturers and students concerning the causes of indiscipline that hinder the effective implementation of the curriculum.

There is no significant difference in the mean scores of teachers and students on the effects of undisciplined on effective curriculum implementation on students in tertiary institutions.

Table 5: t-test analysis of the mean score of teachers and students on the effects of indiscipline which constitute impediments to effective curriculum implementation.

Variables	N	\bar{X}	SD	Dif	T-cal	T-crit	Decision
Lecturers	140	4.66	0.24	369	0.44	1.95	Accept
Students	230	4.64	0.23				

The above hypothesis was accepted because the t-calculated value of 0.44 is less than the critical value of 1.95 at a 0.05 level of significance. Consequently, there is no significant difference between the mean scores of lecturers and students regarding the effect of academic indiscipline as an obstacle to effective curriculum implementation.

Discussion of findings

The data in Table 1 reveals that 85% of the respondents agreed with the statement, which highlighted common disciplinary issues that obstruct effective curriculum implementation among students. This finding aligns with the research of Osakwe (2010) and Abbas (2007), who highlighted that issues such as truancy, vandalism, and examination malpractice have become widespread global challenges. Similarly, studies by Hin & Ijedapo (2011) and Maphosa & Shumba (2010) also pointed out that moral decay is prevalent, indicating that the level of indiscipline has significantly increased. This was further

affirmed by Mohammed (2020) who attributed cases of indiscipline to cultism, vandalism, truancy examination malpractices among others.

The findings in Table 2 show that 90% of respondents agreed with the items identifying the causes of indiscipline, which act as obstacles to effective curriculum implementation among students in tertiary institutions. This was further confirmed by the hypothesis test for significant difference in Table 4, which revealed no significant difference between the mean scores of teachers and students regarding the causes of indiscipline. Research by Sekyere (2009), Mahades (2008), and Ayertey (2002) suggested that the school system, parents, and teachers have significantly contributed to the current rise in indiscipline in schools. These findings align with those of Sekyere (2009), Mahadeo (2008), and Mohammed (2020), who pointed out that factors such as broken homes, peer influence, single parenting, and the financial struggles of parents are linked to indiscipline. These according to Oyovwi (2012) could lead to parent's inadequate provision of infrastructural facilities for their children which in turn impede the implementation of the curriculum.

Table 3 shows that all respondents (100%) agreed with the items outlining the effects of indiscipline on the successful implementation of the curriculum among students in tertiary institutions. This was further supported by the non-significant difference found in the hypothesis test in Table 5. Research by Itsy (2003) and Ayertey (2002) demonstrated that indiscipline behaviors have negatively impacted students' performance in schools. Indiscipline also hampers teachers' ability to perform at their best, as much of their time is spent addressing behavioral issues and ensuring safety within the school environment. This will eventually lead to inadequate coverage of the curriculum content thereby producing half-baked graduates and disruption of the academic program. This finding was in agreement Musa and Martha (2020) who observed that indiscipline affects and reduces teaching thus having a retrogressive repercussion on the academic activities and students performance.

Conclusion

The findings of the study clearly indicated that indiscipline behaviors are widespread in tertiary institutions and significantly impact various aspects of human endeavors, particularly curriculum implementation. As a result, it is crucial for everyone to actively participate in addressing this issue within our institutions and society as a whole. Parents, the government, and schools must refocus on their primary objective: to reform individuals' mindsets and life perspectives, instilling discipline and emphasizing the importance of good social behavior.

Recommendations

The study recommends that;

1. Parents should take responsibility for disciplining their children or wards, both in terms of behavior and academic activities, and instill these values in them.
2. School authorities should establish a student discipline committee to address the misconduct of students in various areas.
3. School authorities should implement rules and regulations that guide both students and staff, ensuring that school policies do not push students to the point of defiance.
4. Parents should be educated on the importance of being responsible and working diligently to fulfill the educational requirements of their children or dependents.
5. Counseling services in tertiary institutions should be strengthened and managed by qualified professionals in the field of counseling.

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